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D9.1

Impact Master Plan

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GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D9.1 Impact Master Plan

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Abstract

This document outlines the project dissemination, communication exploitation strategies for the GenoMed4All H2020 project.

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GenoMed4All project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of contents

Executive summary	6
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose and scope	7
1.2 Document structure.....	8
2 Stakeholder Collaboration Framework	9
2.1 Phases and sprints.....	9
2.1.1 Scout.....	9
2.1.2 Interact.....	10
2.1.3 Learn.....	10
2.2 Key audience and target groups	10
2.2.1 Healthcare professionals	11
2.2.2 Digital service providers.....	12
2.2.3 Advocate initiatives.....	12
2.2.4 Policy makers.....	17
2.2.5 Society as a whole.....	17
2.3 Stakeholders map	17
3 Communication and Dissemination	19
3.1 Communication plan.....	19
3.1.1 Main goals.....	20
3.1.2 Phases and timeline	21
3.1.3 Communication tools and materials	22
3.2 Dissemination plan	27
3.2.1 Main goals.....	28
3.2.2 Phases and timeline	28
3.2.3 Dissemination tools and materials.....	29
4 Exploitation plan	34
4.1 Overview and Strategy	34
4.1.1 What is meant by exploitation?	34
4.1.2 Objective of exploitation.....	34
4.1.3 Exploitation Strategy Guidelines	36
4.1.4 Expected KERs of the project	36
4.2 GenoMed4All's commercial strategy.....	37
4.2.1 Step 1 – Market readiness	37
4.2.2 Step 2 – Business Model	38
4.2.3 <i>Status quo</i> of primary market domains	39
4.3 GenoMed4All's IPR management strategy	40
4.4 GenoMed4All's contribution to standardization	41
4.4.1 Standard candidates.....	42
4.4.2 Collaboration with relevant entities at EU level.....	44
4.5 Value proposition strategy	44
4.6 Segmented Individual exploitation plans	45
4.6.1 Industry	45
4.6.2 SMEs	46

4.6.3	Clinical sites	46
4.6.4	Research.....	47
5	Monitoring of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation efforts	48
5.1.1	C&D database	48
5.1.2	C&D&E tracker	48
5.1.3	Editorial calendar	48
6	Conclusions	50

List of figures

Figure 1.	GenoMed4All's Stakeholder Collaboration Framework	9
Figure 2.	GenoMed4All's key target groups.....	11
Figure 3.	Stakeholder map and segmentation priorities	18
Figure 4.	Communication & Dissemination flows	19
Figure 5.	Communication & Dissemination plan	20
Figure 6.	Phases of GenoMed4All's Communication plan.....	21
Figure 7.	GenoMed4All website – Landing page	23
Figure 8.	GenoMed4All – Twitter profile	24
Figure 9.	GenoMed4All – LinkedIn company page	25
Figure 10.	GenoMed4All – Official YouTube channel	25
Figure 11.	GenoMed4All – Extracts from the weekly check-in mailing campaigns.....	27
Figure 12.	Phases of GenoMed4All's Dissemination plan	28
Figure 13.	GenoMed4All – Open Access community at Zenodo	31
Figure 14.	Timeline for Sprint #1	35
Figure 15.	Timeline for Sprint #2	36
Figure 16.	Business Model Canvas.....	39
Figure 17.	Internal Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation tools	49

List of tables

Table 1.	List of related H2020 projects	16
Table 2.	Main goals for communication.....	21
Table 3.	Communication tools and target audiences.....	23
Table 4.	Dissemination tools and target audiences	30
Table 5.	List of targeted journals.....	31
Table 6.	List of targeted conferences.....	32
Table 7.	List of targeted congresses, exhibitions and demo spaces	33
Table 8.	KER 1 – GenoMed4All technological platform, infrastructure and data sharing modules.....	37
Table 9.	KER 2 – GenoMed4All AI-based services for clinical support	37
Table 10.	Relevant initiatives in genomics and personalized medicine	40
Table 11.	Relevant initiatives in rare disease care	40
Table 12.	Relevant initiatives in Federated Learning.....	40
Table 13.	Bioinformatics and -omics data – standard mapping.....	43

Table 14. Clinical use cases – standard mapping	44
Table 15. Imaging data – standard mapping	44
Table 16. GenoMed4All’s plan for standardization activities	44

Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
HDs	Haematological diseases
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
KERs	Key Expected Results
AI	Artificial Intelligence
HPC	High-Performance Computing
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable sets the framework, guidelines and means for the project's **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation** activities. The proposed document also serves to design and build an *ad hoc* Stakeholder Collaboration Framework, developed to identify the ecosystem of entities impacted by GenoMed4All's innovations and findings.

The **strategies** set out in this document aim to:

- ❑ Ensure the development of appropriate means of communication of the project's results outside of its consortium, with the intention of raising awareness.
- ❑ Increase the project's impact on the identified target audiences, both for further commercial and research purposes.
- ❑ Foster stakeholders' engagement with the consortium, in order to give consistency and continuity to the project's findings and expected outcomes.

Moreover, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plans will also serve an internal purpose, in order for consortium members to always be aware of outreach activities pursued by other partners. These plans will be subject to constant evaluation and revision throughout the duration of the GenoMed4All project, so as to have a constantly updated and accurate depiction of the progress made and challenges ahead.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable (**D9.1 – GenoMed4All Impact Master Plan**), is presented in the framework of GenoMed4All's **WP9 – Impact, Outreach and Collaboration**, specifically within task **T9.1 – Dissemination and communication plans**.

The main goal of WP9 is to fast-track and amplify knowledge transfer between GenoMed4All and its target stakeholder base, reinforcing the value streams of the project and capitalising on the results obtained. The specific **objectives** related to D9.1 are to:

- ❑ Develop and operate a collaboration framework that will enable identifying and building synergies with a range of target groups and communities.
- ❑ Design and implement dissemination and communication strategies to efficiently raise awareness about the outcomes of the project, promoting the activities and results among a critical mass.
- ❑ Assess the footprint of the project through performance indicators, while developing exploitation, sustainability and business models of the key results to be delivered.
- ❑ Develop an effective framework regarding IPR management, technology transfer and fair law enforcement.
- ❑ Actively contribute to relevant standardisation bodies and committees.

D9.1 is the first of a series of WP9 deliverables. This list includes two Dissemination and Communication reports (**D9.2** and **D9.4**) aimed at highlighting the progress of the project's strategy in this sense, and two deliverables regarding the developments of the Exploitation plan (**D9.3** and **D9.5**), to assess the impact of the project's activities in relation to new business opportunities, knowledge creation and standardization.

D9.1 represents GenoMed4All's projection of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategies in the initial stages of the project, hence this can be regarded as a living document, possibly subject to changes during the four-year duration of the project. This is especially relevant for the exploitation of GenoMed4All's results, for two main reasons:

- ❑ Changes in the market structure during the length of the project, requiring to adapt to potentially new market conditions.
- ❑ Emergence of new and innovative standardization opportunities at European and international level.

1.2 Document structure

The present document has been structured in the following way:

- ❑ **Section 1** is the **Introduction**, where the purpose and scope of the document are outlined;
- ❑ **Section 2** is concerned with the **Stakeholder Collaboration Framework**, where the ecosystem of organisations surrounding the project are presented.
- ❑ **Section 3** explains the **Communication and Dissemination** strategy, where the goals, phases, timeline and tools are described.
- ❑ **Section 4** details the **Exploitation plan**, where the foreseen KERs are discussed in the context of the wider exploitation strategies, both by the whole consortium and individual partners.
- ❑ **Section 5** outlines the **Conclusions** of this deliverable, where the final remarks about the strategies are charted.

2 Stakeholder Collaboration Framework

As a H2020 project, GenoMed4All is a decentralised action by nature, but one that still needs to build and navigate an ecosystem of organisations, initiatives and players with a given position of influence on the project's performance and outcomes: its stakeholders. Additionally, it also calls for a responsive growth factor capable of prospecting and creating new synergies over the project's lifetime, facilitating greater exposure and extending its range of action.

To that end, GenoMed4All is implementing an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework**, a methodology designed to continuously develop and strengthen communication streams with key stakeholder groups, empowering the operation of the initiative as introduced in the DoA.

Figure 1. GenoMed4All's Stakeholder Collaboration Framework

2.1 Phases and sprints

This framework's operation follows an iterative approach based on 6-month sprints along 3 phases (**scout**, **interact**, **learn**), to incrementally build and reinforce engagement.

2.1.1 Scout

Building upon GenoMed4All's high-level objectives and findings from previous sprints, this first phase explores, maps and classifies **target groups** (and specific individuals) in terms of their relevance to the scope and impact of the project's work plan. GenoMed4All builds upon the sound experience and active involvement of consortium members in related initiatives, and also on key players that must be considered as the baseline for successful engagement.

It also takes advantage of new leads generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as an outcome of the interacting phase, including emerging PPPs and other related H2020 projects.

The key result from the scouting phase will be the project's **stakeholders map**, a visual mind map to:

- ❑ Identify and list key actors (groups and/or individuals) within the context of the project.
- ❑ Classify and correlate these audiences as per their degree of impact in the project's execution and success.
- ❑ Define a common terminology to be referenced throughout the project's documentation.

2.1.2 Interact

This second phase comprises all interactions with the identified target groups, thus supporting the activities outlined in the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plans for the project. This is the phase where GenoMed4All will collaborate with advocate initiatives in the intersection of **genomics, Artificial Intelligence, High-Performance Computing, haematological diseases and rare diseases**. Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific task forces and working groups, contribute to scientific publications and participate in events. Feedback extracted from previous sprints will be used to improve on the efficiency and impact of these interactions.

2.1.3 Learn

In this last phase, the consortium will learn and adapt based on how these interactions play out and insights obtained from **stakeholder consultation** (i.e., quick surveys or interviews to gather valuable external feedback about the project and its operation). These best practices will in turn feed the next scouting sprint.

2.2 Key audience and target groups

Promoting GenoMed4All and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the initiative requires first an understanding of its target audience. A deep-dive in stakeholder profiles and their influence along the value chain is essential to craft successful Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plans.

Figure 2. GenoMed4All's key target groups

2.2.1 Healthcare professionals

This category includes healthcare professionals and organisations involved in the management and exploitation of genomics and other linked –omics and health data repositories. They require more sophisticated technologies and tools to transform quantitative data into the cause-signs/symptoms and relationships that current approaches fail to produce in diagnostics and treatments.

GenoMed4All will curate multi-sourced data streams into meaningful insights that will enable more robust clinical research and decision making. The involvement of representatives from the health sector is extremely meaningful when it comes to obtaining requirements and feedback to support the implementation of the project, facilitating access to quality data repositories, and supporting direct patient interaction. GenoMed4All will capitalise the participation of 10 top-notch clinical partners, which will serve as the starting point to engage with other organisations in the healthcare sector; namely **medical research centres, healthcare service providers, hospitals, data repository providers, clinics and care centres.**

Our clinical partners:

- ICH – Humanitas Mirasole
- VHIR – Vall d’Hebron Institut de Recerca
- APHP – Assistance Publique - Hôpitaux de Paris
- MLL – Münchner Leukämielabor
- UMCU – UMC Utrecht

- ❑ IBSAL – Institute of Biomedical Research of Salamanca
- ❑ CING – The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics
- ❑ UNIPD – Università degli studi di Padova
- ❑ ULEI – Universität Leipzig
- ❑ NKUA – National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

2.2.2 Digital service providers

GenoMed4All will target organizations involved in disruptive tech, research, business activities or standardisation efforts highly relevant to the application of AI-based technologies and service in the health data, clinical software providers and data aggregators. This category will prioritise actors with a proven track record in responsible development and exploitation of digital transformation in the healthcare domain, namely **large tech**, **MedTech SMEs**, **startups**, **universities** and **RTOs**, **clinical software** providers, **standardisation** and **Open Source** organizations and **data aggregators**.

Our **research** partners:

- ❑ UPM – Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- ❑ UNIBO – Università di Bologna
- ❑ UCPH – Københavns Universitet
- ❑ CRG – Centre for Genomic Regulation
- ❑ UNITO – Università degli Studi di Torino
- ❑ i-HD – The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data
- ❑ FORTH – Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas
- ❑ ESIEE – École Supérieure d'Ingénieurs en Électrotechnique et Électronique
- ❑ CINECA – Cineca Consorzio Interuniversitario

Our **industrial** partners:

- ❑ TF – Thermo Fisher Scientific
- ❑ DEDALUS – Dedalus Healthcare

Our **SMEs**:

- ❑ DW – Datawizard
- ❑ AUS – AUSTRALO

2.2.3 Advocate initiatives

2.2.3.1 EU health networks

Our ambition is to boost accessibility and overall use of data repositories to further research on personalised medicine. For this reason, GenoMed4All will actively seek and benefit from its

partner's links and synergies with multiple organizations and initiatives with access to key networks and resources.

Healthcare and health technology

- ❑ [EIT Health](#) – a KIC (Knowledge and Innovation Community) of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) focusing on health and aging.
- ❑ [EATRIS](#) – European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine
- ❑ [EuroHealthNet](#) – a not-for-profit partnership of public bodies to help build healthier communities and tackle health inequalities across the EU.
- ❑ [European Public Health Association](#) – an umbrella organisation for public health associations and institutes in Europe.
- ❑ [European Connected Health Alliance](#) – the Global Health Connector for Digital Health, facilitating multi-stakeholder connections, driving sustainable change and disruption in the delivery of health and social care.
- ❑ [European Health Management Association](#) - a non-profit organisation to enhance the capacity and capability of health management to deliver high quality healthcare.
- ❑ [EUnetHTA](#) – the European Network for Health Technology Assessment.
- ❑ [MedTech Europe](#) – the European trade association representing the medical technology industries.

Haematological and rare diseases

ERNs are virtual networks involving healthcare providers across Europe. They aim to facilitate discussion on complex or rare diseases and conditions that require highly specialised treatment, and concentrated knowledge and resources. Among the 24 ERNs currently operating, GenoMed4All will leverage synergies with [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), the ERN in **Rare Haematological Diseases** (RHD) EuroBloodNet working on oncological and non-oncological rare haematological diseases (rare anaemias, coagulation disorders, polycythemia, and myeloid and lymphoid tumours). This link will be materialized through our clinical partners, most of which are full members of this network.

ERN-EuroBloodNet is a joint effort between the [European Haematology Association](#) (EHA), the European Network on Rare and Congenital Anaemias (ENERCA), the European haematology patient organisations represented in both the [EURORDIS European Patient Advocacy Groups](#) (ePAGS) and the EHA Patient Organisations Workgroup.

Additionally, GenoMed4All's partners are also part of the following organisations:

- ❑ [ITHANET portal](#) – a resource hub for clinicians and researchers dealing with haemoglobinopathies.
- ❑ [HARMONY Alliance](#) – a Big Data initiative to improve outcomes for patients with blood cancers.
- ❑ [ASH](#) – American Society of Hematology.
- ❑ [SEHH](#) – the Spanish Society for haematology and haemotherapy.

Genomics and precision medicine

The H2020 Advisory Group defines personalised medicine as “a *medical model using characterization of individuals’ phenotypes and genotypes (e.g. molecular profiling, medical imaging, lifestyle data) for tailoring the right therapeutic strategy for the right person at the right time, and/or to determine the predisposition to disease and/or to deliver timely and targeted prevention*”.

Some of the most relevant initiatives in this area (at EU level and beyond) are listed below:

- ❑ [GA4GH](#) – the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health.
- ❑ [EUAPM](#) – the European Alliance for Personalised Medicine.
- ❑ [ICPerMed](#) – International Consortium for Personalised Medicine.
- ❑ [ERA PerMed](#) – an ERA-Net Cofund to align national research strategies, promote excellence, reinforce the competitiveness of European players in precision medicine.
- ❑ [ASH Precision Medicine Initiative](#) – an initiative of the American Society of Hematology to enhance genomic profiling and improve immunotherapies.

2.2.3.2 Related EU projects

Beyond 1M Genomes

GenoMed4All is expected to collaborate closely with funded projects under topic **SC1-HCC-06-2020**: Coordination and Support to better data and secure cross-border digital infrastructures building on European capacities for genomics and personalised medicine.

The winning initiative in this topic is the [Beyond 1M Genomes](#) (B1MG) project. B1MG is helping create a network of genetic and clinical data across Europe. The project provides coordination and support to the [1+ Million Genomes Initiative](#) (1+MG). This initiative is a commitment of 23 European countries to give cross-border access to one million sequenced genomes by 2022.

For GenoMed4All, the opportunity in this collaboration is to contribute to addressing technical specifications and standards for the secure access and exchange of cross-border genomic and other health data. For this, the consortium will look into the possibility of joining the [B1MG Stakeholder Portal](#), a community that includes patient organisations, clinicians, academics and industrial players working on healthcare.

Links to other H2020 projects

There are several other funded projects in H2020 calls working in the intersection of Artificial Intelligence, genomics, precision medicine and patient-centric care, clinical data and decision support systems and tools.

Below is a list of some of those that better suit and/or complement GenoMed4All’s vision:

- ❑ **DT-TDS-04-2020**: AI for Genomics and Personalised Medicine.
- ❑ **DT-TDS-05-2020**: AI for Health Imaging.

- ❑ **SC1-BHC-06-2020:** Digital diagnostics – developing tools for supporting clinical decisions by integrating various diagnostic data.
- ❑ **DT-ICT-12-2020:** AI for the smart hospital of the future.

Topic	Title	Acronym
DT-TDS-04	International consortium for integrative genomics prediction	<u>INTERVENE</u>
	Knowledge At the Tip of Your fingers: Clinical Knowledge for Humanity	<u>KATY</u>
	Pancreatic cancer AI for genomics and personalized Medicine	<u>PANCAIM</u>
	Artificial intelligence Supporting CAncer Patients across Europe	<u>ASCAPE</u>
DT-TDS-05	Accelerating the lab to market transition of AI tools for cancer management	<u>CHAIMELEON</u>
	A European Cancer Image Platform Linked to Biological and Health Data for Next-Generation Artificial Intelligence and Precision Medicine in Oncology	<u>EuCanImage</u>
	A multimodal AI-based toolbox and an interoperable health imaging repository for the empowerment of imaging analysis related to the diagnosis, prediction and follow-up of cancer	<u>INCISIVE</u>
	An AI Platform integrating imaging data and models, supporting precision care through prostate cancer's continuum	<u>ProCAncer-I</u>
SC1-BHC-06	Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment	<u>AI-Mind</u>
	Improved clinical decisions via integrating multiple data levels to overcome chemotherapy resistance in high-grade serous ovarian cancer	<u>DECIDER</u>
	Intelligent Total Body Scanner for Early Detection of Melanoma	<u>iToBoS</u>
	Machine Learning Artificial Intelligence Early Detection Stroke Atrial Fibrillation	<u>MAESTRIA</u>
	Revolution of sleep diagnostics and personalized health care based on digital diagnostics and therapeutics with health data integration	<u>SLEEP REVOLUTION</u>
DT-ICT-12	AI Accelerator – A Smart Hospital Care Pathway Engine	<u>AICCELERATE</u>

	Artificial Intelligence-driven, Decentralized Production for Advanced Therapies in the Hospital	AIDPATH
	Hospital Smart development based on AI	HosmartAI

Table 1. List of related H2020 projects

2.2.3.3 EU research and technology networks

Artificial Intelligence and High-Performance Computing

The European AI Alliance: a multi-stakeholder forum engaged in a broad and open discussion of all aspects of AI development and its impact on the economy and society.

- ❑ [AI4EU](#): the first European Artificial Intelligence On-Demand Platform and Ecosystem.
- ❑ [CLAIRE](#) – a Confederation of Laboratories for AI Research in Europe.
- ❑ [The Big Data Value Association \(BDVA\)](#): an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe.
- ❑ [EuroHPC](#): a Joint Undertaking between the EU, European countries and private partners to develop a world-class supercomputing ecosystem in Europe.
- ❑ [ETP4HPC](#): an industry-led think-tank promoting European HPC research and innovation to support Europe’s competitiveness.

Open Science Access

Open science is a policy priority for the European Commission and the standard method of working under its research and innovation funding programmes as it improves the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research.

- ❑ [European Open Science Cloud](#)
- ❑ [ELIXIR](#) – an intergovernmental organization that brings together life science resources from across Europe.

DIHs – Digital Innovation Hubs

In the context of digital transformation in Europe, DIHs are set up as one-stop shops to help companies become more competitive when creating or improving on their products and services using digital technologies. To fulfil this mission, DIHs provide innovation services, such as financing advice, training and skills development that are needed for a successful digital transformation.

Below is a non-comprehensive list of some DIHs working on the realms of eHealth, AI or cross-border collaboration:

- ❑ [DIHNET](#): project to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

- ❑ [EUHubs4Data](#): the European federation of Data Driven Innovation Hubs for data-driven innovation and experimentation.
- ❑ [DIH-HERO](#): an independent platform connecting DIHs across Europe to create a sustaining network for all those who are active in the healthcare robotics sector.
- ❑ [TechMed Innovation Hub](#): a leading Digital Innovation Hub that stimulates the development and implementation of technology for better healthcare.
- ❑ [eHealth Hub](#): EU-funded cross-border initiative focused on providing business support for the digital health vertical.
- ❑ [DIH-World](#): an initiative to accelerate the uptake of advanced digital technologies by European manufacturing SMEs by supporting them in building sustainable competitive advantages and reaching global markets.

2.2.4 Policy makers

Members of government departments, legislature or any other organizations responsible for creating and enforcing policies and promoting strategies on digital transformation in the healthcare sector. This category includes the **EU Commission**, **Member States**, **National health institutions**, **NHS** and **public health bodies**, **local governments** and **regulatory agencies**, among many others.

2.2.5 Society as a whole

Novel methods and strategies for health and care are powerful ways for improving the quality of life of European society. We will encourage a common understanding on the benefits that digital healthcare brings to patients, incentivising a secure narrative around Artificial Intelligence and its healthcare applications among **patients** and **patient associations**, **non-specialised media** and the **EU citizenship** as a whole.

2.3 Stakeholders map

The figure below depicts the first iteration of the GenoMed4All's stakeholders map. The graph is structured in quadrants for influence and interest/availability, as per the guidelines set out by the Agile Stakeholder Framework:

- ❑ Y-axis shows the mutual **Influence** potential between the project and a specific target group.
- ❑ X-axis depicts the mutual **Interest or Availability** potential between the project and a specific target group.

Figure 3. Stakeholder map and segmentation priorities

3 Communication and Dissemination

Communication and dissemination are at the core of any Horizon 2020 project and GenoMed4All is no exception. A well planned, engaging and agile communication and dissemination plan is one that considers the impact of external factors and challenges (such as the recent Covid-19 crisis) in its execution and effectiveness, and while also unlocking the potential to maximize the project's visibility and reach.

Although communication and dissemination are two interlinked activities, in this document we choose to address them separately, though always in close dependence on one another. It is obvious that similarities and convergences exist and will be examined throughout the whole lifespan of the project.

Figure 4. Communication & Dissemination flows

3.1 Communication plan

GenoMed4All takes into account the versatility and agility of a coherent communication plan and is adopting a funnelled approach to ensure that a targeted but wide communication towards all possible target groups and stakeholders will be deployed. This approach primarily focuses on generating awareness by conveying key aspects and benefits of the project to all target audiences and end users.

Easy to interpret, understand and recognize visual material will be designed and communicated allowing GenoMed4All concepts and benefits to become instantly identifiable to a wider audience while growing and cultivating further interest towards the project and its key outcomes. Additional custom content will be produced and communicated towards specialised target groups to create and maintain an active stakeholders' ecosystem. Similarly, relevant information will be extracted from project deliverables; interviews with partners, pilot case studies; industry reports; and will be relayed through GenoMed4All's communication channels to further support active user engagement.

Figure 5. Communication & Dissemination plan

3.1.1 Main goals

The Communication plan is driven by some key objectives that are crucial to its deployment. Although communication objectives may be treated as a single block, some relate to specific target groups only and thus, will be approached with specific tools and activities throughout the lifespan of the project.

GenoMed4All's **overall objectives for communication** are:

- Increase general awareness and interest about the project to build a solid customer base/ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- Communicate technical, scientific results and benefits to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- Deliver top-level messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of GenoMed4All to reach the widest possible community.

	Boost awareness & interest	Communicate technical & scientific results	Deliver top-level messages about the project	Raise awareness in non-specialised audience
Healthcare professionals	✓	✓		
Digital service providers	✓	✓		
Advocate initiatives	✓		✓	
Related EU projects	✓	✓		
Policy makers	✓	✓	✓	
Society as a whole	✓			✓

Table 2. Main goals for communication

3.1.2 Phases and timeline

Communication activities will be implemented in 3 different phases (**Plan & Revisit**, **Early bird communication** and **Targeted communication**), which are closely related to dissemination as well. The common goal is not only to create “buzz” around the project, but also to mobilise a community of end users which can interact and provide feedback to other project activities as well.

Figure 6. Phases of GenoMed4All's Communication plan

3.1.2.1 Plan & Revisit

The first communication phase will start in M1 of the project and primarily aims at planning all activities, setting up the main communication tools and channels (Website, Social Media), and identifying potential target groups and stakeholders. However, the latter is an activity that will be implemented throughout the whole project. This first phase also includes the concept of revisiting the plan: whenever this is required, the communication plan will be revisited and adjusted according to the needs or circumstances that may exist at a specific period of time. During this phase, initial communication activities (i.e. press releases) will also take place.

3.1.2.2 Early bird communication

The second phase will start in M6. During this phase early bird communication activities will take place aiming to communicate both to a wider public and to specific communities, the existence of the project as an instance and its forthcoming activities and actions. Emphasis will be given to the online tools and measures as they tend to have a wider reach than traditional measures. During this phase, participation for networking purposes to webinars or other online events, articles over the internet about the project (i.e. CORDIS, etc.) will take place. This phase will span the whole duration of the project as it mainly focuses on communicating the generic aspect of the project to a wide stakeholder base.

3.1.2.3 Targeted communication

The third communication phase will start around M12 as it requires the project to be in a relative maturity stage while the first, initial and concrete outcomes are released. During this phase targeted communication activities will take place such as producing and communicating articles, blogs or posts specifically to certain project outcomes and benefits, hosting and/or participating in online events (or physical if possible) for the communication of GenoMed4All's innovations, production of targeted communication material (i.e. videos) for the community, etc. This phase will run in parallel with phase 2 as it focuses on targeted communication actions for specific audiences and not to actions for the whole community.

3.1.3 Communication tools and materials

A series of communication tools will be made available to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a friendly and coherent way. This toolkit will be tailored to specific communication needs for all phases of GenoMed4All's Communication plan.

	Healthcare professionals	Digital service providers	Advocate initiatives	Related EU projects	Policy makers	Society as a whole
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press releases	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Slide decks and one pagers	✓	✓	✓	✓		
General spreading	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Expert networks	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Printed materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multimedia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3. Communication tools and target audiences

3.1.3.1 Online channels

Website

www.genomed4all.eu

Figure 7. GenoMed4All website – Landing page

Public website to showcase the project's main ideas and approach, news, findings and results from our use cases. A key instrument to maximize visibility of the project, introducing visitors to GenoMed4All's rationale and educating them on its concept, the website will also be the main entry point to all public documentation, articles and deliverables. Project findings will be published on the website to showcase its progress and optimise search engine results.

Social media

Twitter: [@genomed4all](#)

LinkedIn: [/genomed4all](#)

YouTube: [YouTube channel](#)

Social media is a fast, low-cost medium to reach interest groups and communities that are normally absent at events or conferences (physical or online). GenoMed4All will create and maintain an active presence in a number of social media channels. **Twitter** and **LinkedIn** have been selected as they have proven to be most effective when engaging with technology communities. A dedicated **YouTube** channel for the project has also been set up, as a way to upload and share GenoMed4All's workshop recordings, official introductory videos and/or any other multimedia content produced throughout the project's run.

Figure 8. GenoMed4All – Twitter profile

Figure 9. GenoMed4All – LinkedIn company page

Figure 10. GenoMed4All – Official YouTube channel

Newsletters

As an engagement tool, online newsletters can provide a sneak-peek into the project's main activities and achievements. To set the stage and achieve wider reach and visibility, a first approach will seek to contribute directly to existing newsletters/magazines with an already established audience in GenoMed4All's main fields of study. The project will also pursue contributing to well-known newsletters by the European Commission or associated initiatives.

Press releases

GenoMed4All will produce and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media as well as other relevant outlets to broadcast and highlight the project's key milestones. The first press release for the project's launch was published in February 2021 and is accessible through [Zenodo](#) and the [News](#) section on the project's website. Press releases will also be shared

internally with project partners so they can use them as reference to communicate the project through their own networks, channels and newsrooms.

Slide decks and one-pagers

Well-designed slide decks or one-pagers of the projects can be a powerful engagement tool to share the project's vision and scope with specialised audiences in a clear, attractive way. GenoMed4All's first slide deck is available through the project's open access community at Zenodo ([here](#)).

General spreading

Publishing online articles, blog posts and other content pieces to various international platforms and communication outlets ([Cordis Wire](#), [Medium](#), [Horizon Magazine](#), [Cordis Research*EU Magazine](#), [MedTech Week Magazine](#)...) and on national/local portals will help maximize the project's visibility and reach.

Expert networks

GenoMed4All will seek to establish synergies with the reference expert networks in AI, HPC, eHealth, precision medicine and haematological diseases, among other realms. In our case, the project counts with the support and active participation of [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), the European Reference Network in Rare Haematological Diseases. This collaboration will help the project gain traction and benefit from valuable resources in terms of communication channels, webinars, databases and networking capabilities.

3.1.3.2 Promotional materials

Printed materials

Brochures, catalogues, posters and any other paper-based resource intended for promotional use. Most of this PR material will be available in a digital format, to be printed out when required (e.g., for display in events, workshops, fairs...). GenoMed4All will also explore other innovative alternatives such as branded merchandise. This strategy has proved to be quite effective in reaching a broader audience, while also encouraging a more sustainable approach when considering long-lasting items.

Multimedia

Multimedia material is a self-explanatory and appealing way of introducing the project to a critical mass through well-known channels (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). Apart from the project's presentation video, a series of video interviews will be set up throughout the project to collect inputs and insights from partners, taking advantage of plenary meetings and other events of note.

3.1.3.3 Internal communication

A clear, effective internal communication strategy is key to ensure that interests are aligned within the consortium and everybody is duly informed of the latest developments.

GenoMed4All's **Weekly check-in** was created as a means to reinforce the project's internal communication channels and make them more engaging. The goal is to have a series of weekly or bi-weekly internal mailing campaigns to keep everyone updated on the project's overall progress and news. Our tool of choice is the [Sendinblue](#) platform, where we periodically design, prepare and send out campaigns for everyone involved in GenoMed4All.

Figure 11. GenoMed4All – Extracts from the weekly check-in mailing campaigns

3.2 Dissemination plan

Dissemination is key for GenoMed4All, as it aims not only to share results with potential users and research peers, the healthcare sector, other digital players and policy makers, but also make these results available to the wider community. To this end, GenoMed4All has developed a flexible dissemination plan that intends to raise awareness of project results, promoting understanding and encouraging action among key target audiences. The execution of this plan

will facilitate the uptake of outcomes and best practices, as well as research insights produced throughout the project's lifetime, thus reinforcing the impacts described in the DoA.

3.2.1 Main goals

Dissemination goals have been previously described in the DoA. These goals are interlinked with those already set for communication activities and also with the overall project objectives: they are all geared towards creating an impact beyond the boundaries of the project.

3.2.2 Phases and timeline

GenoMed4All's Dissemination plan will be implemented in 3 different phases (**Identify & Study**, **Outreach & Influence**, **Embrace & Accept**). The key difference with the Communication plan is that these 3 phases do not span the whole project timeline, but instead have a start and end dates. Of course, this does not rule out the possibility to extend or adjust any of them if necessary or required.

Figure 12. Phases of GenoMed4All's Dissemination plan

3.2.2.1 Identify & Study

During phase 1, GenoMed4All will seek to analyse the project's framework as well as define priorities and actions for the first year of the project, paying special attention to internal and external barriers that might slow down dissemination activities. For this initial phase, a first set of promotional material (produced in the context of GenoMed4All's Communication plan) will be prepared and delivered.

3.2.2.2 Outreach & Influence

The main goal of this second phase is to increase impact and awareness generated during the first phase and showcase GenoMed4All's achievements. All channels will be adequately tailored to find the proper means to engage and collaborate with identified target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results. Participation and/or hosting workshops, *ad hoc* events, tutorials/webinars (if necessary) will boost the dissemination process as a whole. For this phase, specific promotional material will be produced.

3.2.2.3 Embrace & Accept

This final phase will leverage the general awareness raised by the two previous phases, with the aim of attracting more potential end users interested in GenoMed4All's results. All outcomes of the two earlier phases will be evaluated and, if necessary, priorities, measures and dissemination channels will be refined. Participation in events, workshops, conferences, together with partner contributions to publications in targeted specific media online, printed media and research journals will be key to maximize impact and boost visibility.

3.2.3 Dissemination tools and materials

As mentioned, Communication and Dissemination activities are inherently interlinked and therefore some tools are shared between both. Below is the list of specific dissemination tools envisioned for GenoMed4All.

	Healthcare professionals	Digital service providers	Advocate initiatives	Related EU projects	Policy makers	Society as a whole
Project docs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Peer-reviewed publications	✓	✓		✓		
Technical publications	✓	✓		✓		
Open Access repository	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Stakeholder consultation	✓	✓		✓		
Conferences & workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Congresses, exhibitions &	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

demo spaces					
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Table 4. Dissemination tools and target audiences

3.2.3.1 Printed materials

Project documentation

Documentation material in the form of public deliverables will be made available through GenoMed4All open access repository at Zenodo (see 3.2.3.2) and [CORDIS](#), the European Commission's primary source of results from H2020 projects. Public documentation will also be accessible through the project's official website.

Peer-reviewed publications

GenoMed4All intends to publish and contribute to peer-reviewed publications in top scientific journals in our main areas of research. As a Research & Innovation Action, one of our primary goals is to ensure that technical and clinical achievements and experimental findings are adequately showcased and made available to a larger research community and scientific domains, in order to further collaboration and research.

Area	Journal
Clinical	New England Journal of Medicine
Clinical	Journal of Clinical Oncology
Clinical	Blood
Clinical	Blood Advances
Clinical	Hemasphere
Clinical	Leukemia
Clinical	Haematologica
Clinical	The Lancet Haematology
Clinical	American Journal of Hematology
Clinical	British Journal of Hematology
Clinical	Nature Genetics
Clinical	Bioinformatics
Technical	Nature Communications
Clinical	BMC Genomics
Clinical	Journal of the American Medical Association
Technical	IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics
Technical	Journal of Biomedical Informatics (ScienceDirect)
Technical	Journal of Biomedical Informatics (Elsevier)

Technical	IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine
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Table 5. List of targeted journals

Technical publications

Throughout the project’s timeline, partners will publish and contribute with blogs posts, articles, features and more to different outlets: magazines, specialized blogs, LinkedIn, our official website... These kinds of pieces can help disseminate the project’s main ideas and results to a wider audience, thus leveraging its impact.

3.2.3.2 Online channels

Open Access repository

Zenodo: www.zenodo.org/communities/genomed4all-h2020/

Zenodo is a part of the [OpenAIRE initiative](#), Europe’s hub for open access infrastructure research. Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, GenoMed4All will provide open access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data generated within the project, as per our Data Management Plan. There is a dedicated Zenodo community and repository already in place for the project, where we will be uploading publications, public deliverables, data, press releases and more as the project progresses.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the 'GenoMed4All H2020 Project' community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. Below the header, the community name 'GenoMed4All H2020 Project' is prominently displayed. The 'Recent uploads' section lists two items: 'GenoMed4All - Main logo' (uploaded Feb 24, 2021) and 'GenoMed4All - Joint Press Release (Feb 2021)' (uploaded Feb 24, 2021). A 'More' button is located at the bottom of this list. On the right side, a community profile card features the 'GENOMED4ALL' logo, the community name, and a detailed description of the project as an Open Access Repository for the H2020 Grant agreement ID: 101017549. The description highlights the project's goal to transform the response to Haematological Diseases by leveraging Artificial Intelligence and High-Performance Computing.

Figure 13. GenoMed4All – Open Access community at Zenodo

Stakeholder consultation

As part of GenoMed4All’s methodology for an Agile Stakeholder Framework (see section 2 - Learn phase), the project will set up surveys and opinion polls among key actors to collect feedback about critical needs and potential issues (validation of priorities, execution...). This will allow a broader view on the project’s ambition and scope and insights on how to better tailor dissemination actions to a specialised audience.

3.2.3.3 Events

Below is an indicative list of events that have been identified by the GenoMed4All consortium as main targets. This list will be continuously updated with inputs from partners and depending on the maturity of the project at a given stage. It is also worth noting that right now, the majority of events are pivoting to the online scene, as a consequence of the current Covid-19 pandemic.

Conferences

The consortium will disseminate outcomes by means of presentations, talks and personal engagement. This includes participation in dedicated events, such as conferences, workshops and trade fairs as a strategic mechanism to actively interact and engage with multiple stakeholders at a time.

Area	Conference	Date	Location
Technical	AI World – The future of AI	14-07-2021	Virtual
Clinical	ISMB/ECCB 2021 Conference	25-07-2021	Virtual
Technical	VLDB 2021 International Conference	16-08-2021	Copenhagen (DK)
Clinical	DGHO Annual meeting 2021	01-10-2021	Berlin (DE)
Technical	IEEE EMB 2021 International Conference	31-10-2021	Virtual
Clinical	ASH Annual Meeting & Exposition 2021	11-12-2021	Atlanta (US)
Clinical	ESH Conferences	Multiple	Multiple
Clinical	Dutch Hematology Congress	19-01-2022	Papendal (NL)
Clinical	EHA Virtual Congress	09-06-2022	TBD
Clinical	ESHG Virtual Conference	28-08-2021	Virtual
Technical	AI World Conference & Expo	2022	Boston (US)
Clinical	AACR Annual Meeting	2022	TBD
Technical	IEEE CBMS International Symposium	2022	TBD
Technical	ML Conference	2022	TBD

Table 6. List of targeted conferences

Congresses, exhibitions and demo spaces

GenoMed4All will target specific events in the realms of AI, eHealth, precision medicine and genomics, in order to showcase the project's most tangible outcomes (platform, AI-based services...) to a wider audience through exhibitions and demonstrations.

Event	Date	Location
AI & Big Data Expo Global	06-09-2021	London (UK)
Health Data Forum	27-10-2021	Porto (PT)
AI & Big Data Expo Europe	23-11-2021	Amsterdam (NL)
Future Health Summit	22-09-2021	Dublin (IE)
European Alliance for Personalised Medicine	Multiple	Multiple
EATRIS events	Multiple	Multiple
Medtech Week	2022	TBD
European Congress on Digital Pathology	2022	TBD
EACR Congress	2022	TBD
Digital Health World Congress	2022	TBD
HIMSS & Health Europe	2022	TBD

Table 7. List of targeted congresses, exhibitions and demo spaces

4 Exploitation plan

4.1 Overview and Strategy

4.1.1 What is meant by exploitation?

Under **Article 28.1** on the Exploitation of Results of the Grant Agreement, the consortium must take measures to ensure the exploitation of the results up to four years after the end of the project. This includes the following use of the results:

- Application in further research activities (outside the action).
- Development, creation or marketing of a product or process.
- Service creation and provision.
- Use in standardisation activities.

According to the H2020 glossary, the term exploitation is defined as “*the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities*”. Therefore, the objective of exploitation is to “effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society”.

The project results are defined as “*any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights*”.

4.1.2 Objective of exploitation

The GenoMed4All objectives for the exploitation plan have been set out at the proposal stage, aiming to maximize the project’s impact on different layers of EU society. The project’s ambition is to act as an enabler that will lead to cost-effective AI solutions that are interoperable in large-scale clinical service investments, beginning with haematological diseases (HDs), but expecting to pave the way for a more intense use of AI to achieve meaningful outcomes for advancing research and personalised medicine. Therefore, exploitation will focus around the objective of clinical application and exploitation in the traditional sense of triggering innovation and entrepreneurship.

In order to reflect the project’s ambition to successfully exploit the project’s result for further use, the Exploitation plan envisions the drafting of five documents, delivered in two different “steps”, that aim to contextualize the project’s activities, in relation to the objective of WP9. The two steps are:

Sprint #1

The output of Sprint #1 is represented by **D9.3 – Interim GenoMed4All Impact assessment, exploitation and sustainability report**. The objective of Sprint #1 is double: on one end, to

internally validate the relevant stakeholders which might have an interest in the KERs of the project and the nature of their interest (commercial, research...), as well as defining a specific value proposition on the project's results for each segment. On the other hand, it aims to assess the state of the landing markets of GenoMed4All's innovations. The goal is to have a comprehensive and valuable document whose accuracy can benefit from the almost two years' involvement of the partners in the project. Sprint #1 will thus encompass the following documents:

- ❑ **Project's ecosystem:** a mapping of all the various social segments with a potential interest in the KERs of the project;
- ❑ **Market readiness:** assessment of market conditions, including Market Readiness Level (MRL), competition landscape and the identification of sustainable business models;
- ❑ **Value Proposition:** definition of a specific value proposition for the KERs with great commercial and research potential. The objective is to assess whether the different segments have an interest or not in them, as well as defining the nature of such eventual interest.

Figure 14. Timeline for Sprint #1

Sprint #2

Sprint #2 is intended to build upon the outcomes from Sprint #1 and exploit their validated knowledge, mainly in relation to the triggering of innovation and entrepreneurship. In this sense, both the legal and commercial aspects related to the project will be addressed. The related documents will be published within **D9.5 – Final GenoMed4All impact assessment, exploitation and sustainability report**, and will encompass:

- ❑ **Business Plan:** definition of a valid business model canvas for each specific KER with commercial value. The objective is to identify and implement financial sustainability to ensure the continuity of GenoMed4All activities in the long-term after termination of the Horizon 2020 funding period. The proposed business model will be focal to bring the project's innovation to market.
- ❑ **IPR and Knowledge Management assessment:** this document will discuss the activities related to the use and exploitation of the project results and knowledge, from a knowledge-creation perspective. It will include both consortium-wide activities and individual attempts.

Figure 15. Timeline for Sprint #2

4.1.3 Exploitation Strategy Guidelines

The GenoMed4All projects foresees exploitation in a wide variety of ways, which need to be linked to one of the following means:

- ❑ **Financial exploitation:** building products, projects, or services based on the project results.
- ❑ **Research & development:** by engaging in new research projects, based on the experiences gained in the activities. The projects can be EU or nationally funded, as well as sponsored by other sources, such as industry or charity.
- ❑ **Education** (e.g., courses, additional lessons) at the school or university level, or in continuing education, etc.
- ❑ **Community building:** around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions.
- ❑ **Knowledge transfer:** from academia to industry, by collaboration or via employees, to realities outside the EU.
- ❑ **Contributions to open-source projects and standardization:** providing public access to the mix-net framework and encouraging its broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties.
- ❑ **Contribution to the promotion of an ethical use of AI in the healthcare field:** mainly in relation to GDPR and MDR compliance.

On the side of the official project's exploitation strategy, individual members of the consortium are highly incentivized to pursue individual attempts to exploit the project's results. A more detailed analysis of those potential attempts of individual exploitation in Section 4.6.

4.1.4 Expected KERs of the project

In the proposal phase, the consortium identified the following KERs as the main outputs upon which to conduct the exploitation process of the project:

KER 1	GenoMed4All technological platform, infrastructure and data sharing modules
KER 1.1	Technological modules for automatic data curation, storage and enrichment for health and genomic data standardization
KER 1.2	Cross-border data infrastructure and servers that allow secure, interoperable management of sensitive genomics and health data.

KER 1.3	Training of Machine Learning algorithms using HPC and Federated Learning.
KER 1.4	Orchestrator for ensuring compliance with national and European regulations for data privacy.

Table 8. KER 1 – GenoMed4All technological platform, infrastructure and data sharing modules

KER 2	GenoMed4All AI-based services for clinical support
KER 2.1	Diagnostic algorithms for early identification of individuals at high risk of developing MDS.
KER 2.2	Prediction/Prognostic-algorithms providing information on disease development for MDS and SCD.
KER 2.3	Clinical decision-making support algorithms for risk stratification of individually customized therapies for MDS and SCD patients.
KER 2.4	Diagnostic, prediction, prevention and clinical decision-making support algorithms tested on MM, which will serve as a pilot to evaluate reusability and result extrapolation to haematological diseases with higher incident rates.

Table 9. KER 2 – GenoMed4All AI-based services for clinical support

4.2 GenoMed4All's commercial strategy

The GenoMed4All consortium intends to set up a commercial strategy that allows to conceptualize and validate the best means for the adoption in the market of its innovative outputs. The market integration of the project's KERs through commercialization plays an essential role in reaching the objective of providing robust, established and continuous improvements in the healthcare industry.

The timeframe for the market adoption and penetration of the envisioned outputs is mid- to long-term. Two main reasons have shaped the definition of such timeframe:

- ❑ The early stage of the project does not allow to have a clear-enough vision of the final version of the output, requiring the more accurate vision that will be possible by the end of Step 1.
- ❑ As of the 4-year lifetime of the project and the ever-changing nature of markets, the consortium needs to evaluate the state of the various target markets in conditions as close as possible to the ones when commercialization.

For these reasons, the commercialization strategy has been split into two different steps: market readiness and business model.

4.2.1 Step 1 – Market readiness

Within the commercial strategy of GenoMed4All, one whole task is dedicated to the assessment of the status of the markets that the project outcomes aim to target. The intended exploitable

results comprehend the technological platform, infrastructure and data sharing modules on one end, and the AI-based services for clinical support on the other. It will be fundamental for the correct execution of the envisioned commercialization strategy to accurately analyse the market conditions that will be encountered, in order to exploit eventual opportunities and mitigate the risks.

This analysis will be carried out according to the following methodology:

- ❑ Research of both primary and secondary sources of data (reports, white papers, interviews etc.) in order to have the numbers and figures regarding the specific markets.
- ❑ Interviews and workshops with industry partners with first-hand commercial experience in those markets. The aim is to gather valuable insights about the state of the markets. The potential interviewees and participants can be either members of the GenoMed4All consortium or strategic partners identified through the project's ecosystem.

The foreseen output of this task, which will be part of **D9.3 – Interim GenoMed4All Impact assessment, exploitation and sustainability report**, is a comprehensive document that accurately discusses the state of the different target markets, the solutions already present in the market, who the dominant players are, sustainable business models...

4.2.2 Step 2 – Business Model

The Business Model represents the final output related to the commercial strategy here discussed. It consists of a well-defined, complete document, structured according to the **Business Model canvas** structure, for each exploitable output of the GenoMed4All project. Some of the information needed to fill the canvas will be collected through the activities related to Sprint #1 (mainly the Market readiness and Value proposition documents).

The rest will be collected through **workshops** and **focus groups** aimed at gathering the data required to fill the different sections of the canvas. In this sense, the whole canvas has been divided into 4 different themes, united by the specific topic addressed. Each one of the themes will require a leader that has an accurate view on a specific realm of the project (industrial, clinical...), coming from a 2 years' experience of direct involvement in the project.

These themes are shown in the canvas below, and have been defined as:

- ❑ **Theme 1 – Value Proposition:** comprising the *Value Proposition* and *Customer Segments* sections, decisively builds upon data from Step 1 data.
- ❑ **Theme 2 – Addressing the market:** including the sections on *Customer Relationships* and *Channels*, will be led by an industrial partner with market experience.
- ❑ **Theme 3 – Internal Analysis:** for the sections about *Key Partners*, *Key Activities* and *Key Resources*, will be led by a technical partner with a holistic view on the project's commercial outputs.
- ❑ **Theme 4 – Financial Approach:** comprising the *Cost Structure* and *Revenue Streams* sections, will be led by an industrial partner with a holistic view on the project specific output.

Figure 16. Business Model Canvas

4.2.3 Status quo of primary market domains

The consortium has identified three primary market domains targeted by GenoMed4All's innovations:

- Genomics and Personalised Medicine.
- Rare Disease Care.
- Technology Engineering – Federated Learning Systems and Platforms.

These are all significant, hot, growing markets right now with a number of key players and trends that need to be assessed, especially in the context of their change throughout the duration of the project. By confronting the state of the market through the Market Readiness document with the current one, the consortium will be able to more precisely position itself according to the strategies of other relevant players in the various markets. Therefore, in the early stages of the project, the following market activities have been regarded as relevant:

4.2.3.1 Genomics and Personalised Medicine

Initiative	Details
Genomedics	Clinical Governance, Research and clinical-epidemiological analysis.
Allelica	Platform for Polygenic Risk Score analysis and reporting.
Eurofins Genomics	Genomics webshop.
Color Genomics	Partnership with ThermoFisher in the US.

23&Me	Genomics testing linked with healthcare.
Nvidia	NVIDIA Clara™ healthcare platform.
Freemome	Multi-omics blood test for cancer.
Syapse	Real World Evidence for Personalised Medicine.
Drug-PIN	Tool for personalized prescription of medicines.

Table 10. Relevant initiatives in genomics and personalized medicine

4.2.3.2 Rare disease care

Initiative	Details
Mendelian	Improving rare disease diagnosis.
Pfizer	Rare disease treatment.
Moderna	Rare disease treatment.
Bayer	R&D focus on innovative targets for hemophilia, rare blood disorders, acute bleeding and hemoglobinopathies.
European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP RD)	Programme aiming to create an effective rare diseases research ecosystem for progress, innovation and for the benefit of everyone with a rare disease.

Table 11. Relevant initiatives in rare disease care

4.2.3.3 Federated Learning technology/engineering

Initiative	Details
Iomed	Federated database for electronic health records.
MELLODY	Predictive Machine Learning models on decentralized data for drug discovery.
Musketeer	Machine learning platform tested and validated in two different industrial scenarios: Smart manufacturing and Healthcare.
ESCAPE	Federated data infrastructure of Open Access of astronomy and particle physics data.

Table 12. Relevant initiatives in Federated Learning

4.3 GenoMed4All's IPR management strategy

GenoMed4All has the ambition to set up an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP) generated throughout the length of the project. The internal entity responsible for

the definition of matters surrounding IPR is the Project Management Office (PMO), which will support the Project Officer in the supervision of the Consortium-wide knowledge management activities.

Moreover, GenoMed4All highly encourages its members to explore individual opportunities of knowledge creation, on top of the project's results. These activities are regulated under the Consortium Agreement (CA) through the basic principle of **foreground knowledge**, which allows the project partner which solely contributes to the development of new knowledge to be able to exploit it according to its own will.

Nonetheless, in the case of a joint development of knowledge, the ownership of the innovative knowledge will be regulated under the Joint Ownership Agreements, unless the contractor concerned agrees on a different solution. The granting of Access Rights to jointly owned foreground will be royalty-free and the granting of Access Rights to own foreground will either be royalty-free based on fair and reasonable conditions, defined by the PMO. Moreover, the European Community will be granted a non-exclusive royalty-free license to access to the GenoMed4All findings, in order to be able to generate interest around the project's public knowledge materials such as reports, methodologies or case material.

The GenoMed4All strategy in relation to IPR Management consists of three distinct elements, envisioned to ensure the highest possible level of IP protection:

- ❑ A system that enables the **protection of IP** (e.g., patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR),
- ❑ A **technology transfer framework**, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the European IPR Helpdesk.
- ❑ A **fair law enforcement system** in each partner's country that caters to dispute settlement but also that can award penalties and sanctions.

This internal mechanism aims at regulating the management of knowledge created during the project and is designed to grant the most flexible framework possible to allow partners with a commercial interest in the project to pave the way for exploitation. All activities related to IPR will be summarized in deliverable **D9.5**, in the context of **Step 2**.

4.4 GenoMed4All's contribution to standardization

GenoMed4All will participate in the efforts of already existing standardization bodies aiming to implement innovative frameworks in fields related to the project. Two main standardization trajectories have been identified as relevant regarding the outcome of the project, thus will pave the way of the standardization efforts:

- ❑ Genomic standardization led by **WP8**.
- ❑ Clinical data standardization led by **WP5**.

GenoMed4All will implement the common data standards framework across platforms for genomics data standards for machine-learning approaches. It will also implement standards for cross-platform data integration to develop innovative solutions from bench to bedside.

The consortium is always scouting for opportunities to exploit its findings for the development of standards that fall into the scope of the two identified trajectories. The responsible WPs have already identified a series of standardization bodies (see sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2) that will be impacted by GenoMed4All's generated knowledge.

However, the early stage of the project makes it impossible to accurately predict the whole spectrum of target bodies. The Consortium intends to provide public access to the mix-net framework to encourage its results' broad adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties. WP8 and WP5 will lead the activities related to standardization.

Most partners in the consortium are already members of such standardization bodies, hence the project can build on an already established base. Further opportunities will be explored through periodic activity reporting, identifying significant opportunities to push contributions into future standard and pre-normative activities, both in the ICT and eHealth domains. Individual opportunities by the consortium members, if previously agreed internally, will be highly incentivized, in line with the project's intention to maximize its results' impacts.

Through **D8.3 – GenoMed4All standardization final report**, the consortium aims to provide a holistic view of all the standardization opportunities explored throughout the whole length of the project. The emphasis will be put on the impacted bodies and the final outcome of the process, therefore accurately contextualizing how GenoMed4All knowledge has been exploited for standardization activities.

4.4.1 Standard candidates

Defining a consistent and sustainable data strategy is key for GenoMed4All, since the project covers a vast data spectrum from genomics to various clinical data formats. Main challenges identified at this early stage are:

- ❑ A Federated Learning model that requires a common data model shared by all data providers.
- ❑ A need to establish links between genomic and clinical data to develop better AI models.
- ❑ The fragmentation of the clinical data space: there is a requirement to aggregate data from several clinical sites operating with different data models and overlaps depending on the use case (clinical, research...).

4.4.1.1 Bioinformatics and the -omics pipeline

Standard	Data types (tentative scope)	Details
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VCF		Variant Call Format specifications, the format of a text file used in bioinformatics for storing gene sequence variations.
BAM		Binary Alignment Map (BAM) is the compressed binary representation of the raw data of genome sequencing.
FastQ		FASTQ is a text-based format that stores a biological sequence and its corresponding quality scores.
Beacons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Cytogenetics <input type="checkbox"/> Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) Analysis <input type="checkbox"/> DNA variant calling <input type="checkbox"/> RNA sequencing <input type="checkbox"/> Genome assembly 	Beacons are a GA4GH initiative for the federated discovery of genomic data in biomedical research and clinical applications while maintaining the privacy of human genomics data.
OpenWDL		OpenWDL is the community behind Workflow Description Language (WDL), a way to specify data processing workflows, originally for genome analysis pipelines.
CWL		Common Workflow Language (CWL) is used to define workflows to automate complex genome analyses.
GA4GH WES		The Workflow Execution Service (WES) API describes a way to run the same workflow using various execution platforms and environments.

Table 13. Bioinformatics and -omics data – standard mapping

4.4.1.2 Clinical use cases

Standard	Data types (tentative scope)	Details
HL7 FHIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Demographic data <input type="checkbox"/> Haematology data (clinical and diagnostic reports) <input type="checkbox"/> Haematology risk assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Demographic data 	Fast Health Interoperable Resources (FHIR) is a next generation standards framework created by HL7 and built from a set of modular components called <i>resources</i> . It comprises: a data model for healthcare data exchange, server technology and a RESTful API.
Phenopackets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Haematology data (clinical and diagnostic reports) <input type="checkbox"/> Haematology risk assessment 	Phenopackets are an open standard approved by GA4GH for sharing disease and phenotype information to improve our ability to understand,

		diagnose, and treat both rare and common diseases.
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Table 14. Clinical use cases – standard mapping

4.4.1.3 Imaging data

Standard	Data types (tentative scope)	Details
ICHOM	MRI/PET imaging	Improved standards for self-reported patient data and potentially new standard sets proposed to the International Consortium for Health Outcomes Management (ICHOM) for patient-centric care.

Table 15. Imaging data – standard mapping

4.4.2 Collaboration with relevant entities at EU level

Entity	Details
European Reference Networks (ERNs)	ERN-EuroBloodNet and their transversal working groups on Patients Registries. Standardisation of common data elements for rare diseases and domain specific (haematology), including definition and codification schemes for disease, phenotype and genetic variants.
GA4GH	The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) is a policy-framing and technical standards-setting organization, seeking to enable responsible genomic data sharing within a human rights framework.
StandICT.eu 2023	The initiative to create a European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem building on the success of the StandICT.eu initiative, with a community of 700+ members, open calls to empower contributions from ICT standardisation experts and a dedicated Standards Observatory (EUOS) .

Table 16. GenoMed4All's plan for standardization activities

4.5 Value proposition strategy

The presence of a wide variety of different actors both in the consortium and in the GenoMed4All ecosystem suggest that the results' value will be rather asymmetrical for each specific target group. In this sense, it becomes an impossible task to define a Value Proposition statement valid for all the actors involved, requiring us to take a more agile and segmented approach.

Therefore, GenoMed4All will organize dedicated interactive workshops inviting members of each specific target group (selected through the project's Ecosystem), to participate and impact the discussion around which is the specific value that the project has on their activities. The value is double.

On one end, it allows to engage entities strictly connected to the project's scope and empower them with information about the GenoMed4All activities, generating interest and awareness on the project. On the other, it allows the consortium (and WP9 more specifically) to gather perspective from a wide variety of specific entities to increase the accuracy of the developed Value Proposition:

- Industry
- SMEs
- Clinical sites
- Research
- Policy makers

The findings gathered through such workshops fall in the scope of Sprint #1, thus will be published within **D9.3**. They will serve as the base upon which to take any decision regarding the commercialization strategy of GenoMed4All. If commercial interests regarding a project's KER emerge from a specific segment, then this information will be exploited to build a business case that will be published in **D9.5** within the business model canvas.

4.6 Segmented Individual exploitation plans

This section outlines each foreseen individual Exploitation plan of GenoMed4All's results. The public nature of this document requires the segmentation of each plan into the wider category, in order to safeguard each partners' privacy. Nonetheless, the wider consortium encourages each partner to plan the exploitation of the results by either:

- The creation of further research activities.
- Developing, creating or marketing a process or a product.
- Creating and providing a marketable service.
- Supporting the wider adoption among the EU member states of AI tools in the healthcare field.

4.6.1 Industry

Through the participation in the GenoMed4All project, industry partners have the aim to bridge the gap between industry and academic innovation, in the use of AI in the healthcare field.

- The industrial partners seek to strengthen their strategic positioning in the hematologic field and health industry by the knowhow gathered through the GenoMed4All activities.
- Increase the level of their services marketplace by incorporating the project's AI services, federating learning approach and the HPC infrastructure in their offers.

- ❑ Integrating GenoMed4All's newly developed modules in their existing health technology platforms.

4.6.2 SMEs

The SMEs present in the GenoMed4All, due to their flexible and innovative business models, seek to experiment and discover innovative solutions in the field of personalized medicine, deep learning and AI, upon which to build innovative services.

- ❑ Exploit the possibility to participate in such RIA initiative to expand the market offers as strategic players in Europe for application of a Human-centric design.
- ❑ Exploit the GenoMed4All results to enrich their business portfolio.
- ❑ Exploiting the knowledge gained from the project to bridge Research and Innovation and the market, mainly in relation to the development of marketing services and ecosystem dynamization.
- ❑ Expand the range of services towards other customers and partners, at European and international range.

4.6.3 Clinical sites

The clinical members of the GenoMed4All consortium have as their priority to promote and raise awareness about the project's contents, developments and results to established communities (at local, national and international level), in association with a specific communication and dissemination strategy.

- ❑ Cooperate with decision-making bodies and organizations identifying specific channels for exploitation events in Europe and internationally.
- ❑ Get patients involved and continue their involvement by creating value from the patients' point of view.
- ❑ Engaging in business exploitation activities, such as developing new technology transfers, licensing, creation of start-ups and acceleration of innovation in general.
- ❑ Engaging in legal exploitation activities, such as IPR, data protection, revision of Consortium Agreements and creation of new collaborations with industrial partners.
- ❑ Engage clinical research regarding HDs, in the frame of ERN-EuroBloodNet and its members through the platform.
- ❑ Engage clinical research for other related diseases, using the GenoMed4All infrastructure to improve research workflows.
- ❑ Exploit the project's methodology for future research activities and studies that heavily rely on the presence of large amounts of genomic data as an extent to our ongoing efforts in the fields of AI in medicine.
- ❑ Promote personalized medicine and targeted treatment for patients with rare disorders linked to haematological disorders (such as haemophilia and leukaemia), through the knowledge and infrastructure developed in the GenoMed4All project.

- ❑ Exploit GenoMed4All's outcomes to expand the range of diagnostic services, in the context of personalized interpretation of genetic variation for each individual.

4.6.4 Research

The research partners of GenoMed4All intend to exploit the developed machine and statistical learning algorithms for HDs, including AI techniques based on Neural Networks, Deep Learning and Graph theory.

- ❑ Exploit the machine learning and federated learning methods developed in this project, such as the data pre-processing pipelines, the data representations developed and the learning paradigm, including learning of custom representations also federated learning.
- ❑ Exploit the projects' anonymized and GDPR-compliant data from hospitals and labs for projects with similar scope, from the GenoMed4All's platform.
- ❑ Exploit GenoMed4All's developed algorithms for the diagnosis of HDs through their integration in already existing Platforms and datasets of rare diseases data.
- ❑ The set-up and scale-up of a dedicated AI European Infrastructure will broaden the user base of computing resources and will allow to develop and validate AI models in the field for the migration from project oriented to service-oriented compute resource provisioning.
- ❑ Support, through the knowledge generated in the project, the clinical research community in the field of HDs.

5 Monitoring of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation efforts

Continuous monitoring and customization of both the Communication and the Dissemination and the Exploitation Plan are fundamental elements of GenoMed4All's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to anticipate and mitigate any deviations affecting the project's timeline or its resources. It also addresses potential implementation issues and helps assess whether further action is required to ensure objectives are met. On this topic, the consortium will focus on the pre-assessment of information needs, monitoring frequency and a methodology for collecting evidence.

The execution and effectiveness of these plans is dependent on close monitoring, flexible and prompt response mechanisms. Impact KPIs have already been defined for these areas, though they remain confidential and have only been disclosed to the European Commission's representatives and shared internally within GenoMed4All's consortium. In this sense, **internal Communication and Dissemination reporting tools** and **resources** have also been made available to all partners involved, so that they may report and track their individual Communication and Dissemination efforts. These tools will also host and aid the reporting and follow-up on **Exploitation-related efforts**, such as: publications on standardization mechanisms, white papers on key results, demos and exhibitions for GenoMed4All's platform and services...

5.1.1 C&D database

An internal database listing all shared resources available in each partners' networks: newsletters and magazines, journals, conferences and events. This database will serve as a common knowledge base for Communication & Dissemination efforts.

5.1.2 C&D&E tracker

A simple tracker to list and report all efforts linked to communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project and its results. This is a collective effort to which all partners should contribute. Whenever a partner participates in a communication or dissemination action/activity or dedicates efforts/resources to contribute and drive the project's exploitation strategy, it needs to be reported to keep full traceability and collect evidence for the European Commission.

5.1.3 Editorial calendar

An internal calendar to plan out content for the project's expected articles (short pieces linked to milestones, general progress and/or findings) and agree on the best publication dates and platforms (project website, blogs, social media...). This tool will also help keep track of all external mentions, articles or press features on the project.

C&D database

Contribute to the list of newsletters, magazines, journals, conferences & events

C&D&E tracker

Report all your communication, dissemination & exploitation activities

Editorial calendar

A planner for articles, blog posts and other contributions from partners

Figure 17. Internal Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation tools

In order to provide a bird's eye view into GenoMed4All's exploitation activities, the consortium will also make use of the project's already available online channels:

- ❑ **GenoMed4All's website:** through the project's official website, we have the ambition to keep a constant communication flow about our exploitation activities to the wider EU society. The website will allow people to easily access relevant documents, public strategies and reports related to our exploitation activities.
- ❑ **GenoMed4All's social media:** the adoption of a communication strategy involving social media like LinkedIn and Twitter facilitates reaching out to the wider EU society in a direct, informal manner, while also allowing the general public to be informed about individual and consortium-wide exploitation activities.

6 Conclusions

This document has outlined GenoMed4All's **Stakeholder Collaboration framework** and **Communication and Dissemination** strategies, as well as the project's approach towards **Exploitation** of results for business, standardization and IPR purposes. All these tasks fall into the scope of WP9, with WP8 leading the project's standardization efforts.

During its 4-year run, the project requires a well-defined approach to these activities, mainly in relation to its target audience for outreach activities, the best approach to stimulate adoption of generated knowledge and a viable timeframe for all activities related to WP9. In this sense, D9.1 clearly defines the roles, objective and timing of GenoMed4All's outreach strategies.

With regards to the **Stakeholder Collaboration framework**, GenoMed4All's impact has been identified and evaluated across a wide spectrum of entities, encompassing policy makers, society as a whole, digital service providers, healthcare professionals and advocate initiatives. The aim is to understand the ecosystem of actors which might be interested in the project's findings, in order to develop a specific value proposition for each category to disseminate them.

Moreover, the proposed **Communication and Dissemination plan** has been designed with an agile communication methodology in mind, which:

- ❑ Internally, will allow for a smooth coordination of tasks between different WPs.
- ❑ Externally, will enable an effective dissemination of results in a manner that generates engagement in target audiences.

In this sense, GenoMed4All's social media accounts and the official website will serve as main external engagement tools.

Additionally, the **Exploitation** strategy presented in this document is based upon three main areas of action: business, standardization and IPR. The objectives of the foreseen plan are to exploit GenoMed4All's KERs for commercial purposes through the definition of a sustainable and realistic business model, both at consortium level and individually for each partner.

Standardization activities are meant to bring genomics standardization and data models for other -omics data into the wider context of European research activities on the matter. Finally, due to the innovative nature of the foreseen KERs, a solid framework for the legal protection of all generated knowledge must be observed.

This document will thus serve as a preliminary roadmap for consortium members to carry out their specific communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Due to its release in the early stages of the project, the concretization of certain aspects of these strategies might be subject to changes throughout the length of the project. Therefore, this can be considered as a living document and any and all changes will be adequately reflected in successive iterations of upcoming deliverables **D9.2** and **D9.4** (Interim and Final Dissemination and Communication reports).

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